

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR LOGICAL THINKING

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Abstract. *The reason why school education has become an object of fundamental reforms in recent years is the goal of reforming the education sector starting from the lower level and raising the quality level. First of all, this requires the development of worldview and logical thinking of future and active pedagogues of the field. Logical thinking is an important vital factor for every person, regardless of his age and professional activity. Because the mind is one of the greatest gifts given to man, and its correct use in the process of solving every day events and various issues depends on the level of development of logical thinking in a person. This article deals with the methodical preparation of future elementary school teachers for logical thinking and pedagogical conditions in this process.*

Keywords: *future primary school teachers, thinking, logical thinking, pedagogical conditions.*

INTRODUCTION

At the same time as the construction of new Uzbekistan and the third renaissance period are passing, the school education system, which is one of the lowest and basic levels in the field of education, has many areas that need updating and reform. It is worth noting that the low level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of children in primary education is mainly explained by the imperfection of modern teaching methods and forms in primary education. For this reason, when talking about attracting competent personnel in the educational process, we should first of all remember the necessity of technologicalization of the primary education system, the introduction of information and computer technologies, electronic educational tools to the school.

Logical thinking is the ability of a person to think carefully about the tasks in front of him and to make quick and non-standard solutions from the point of view of pedagogy, and to try to find the best and effective ways to achieve his goals. That is, logic is mainly calculated to come up with ideas that are not like others, to avoid traditional thinking and to know ways to quickly and effectively solve problematic situations. Despite the fact that it is an aspect related to the concept of creativity, it encompasses some very detailed and deep considerations. Logical thinking consists of the combination of individual qualities and thinking abilities that form the basis for the formation and development of creative abilities in a person.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Various aspects of primary education in our republic were actively researched by B.S.Abdullaeva, B.R.Adizov, G.R.Akramova, G.T.Boymurodova, N.G'.Dilova, G.N.Najmiddinova, X.P.Nazarova.

Fundamental research on the development of students' logical thinking at the primary level of education, the professional development of teachers in this process by pedagogues-scientists B. Khodjaev, R. Djuraev, O. Gazman, E. Zeer, L. Tarita, It was carried out by Ye. Kazakova, Ye. Aleksandrova, M. Pevzner, A. Maslow, A. Kombas and others.

Pedagogists-scientists A.Abduqadirov, R.Djuraev, U.Inoyatov, O.Musurmonova, Kh.Ibraimov, Sh.Abdullaeva, D.Ro'zieva, D.Sharipova and others researched various aspects of intellectual development of future specialists

In order to become a pedagogue who can meet the modern requirements, the future elementary school teacher needs to acquire computer skills and realize that he will have a unique assistant in his work. Using information and communication technologies in the educational process, we solve the following tasks:

- gaining interest and motivation to study;
- formation of educational qualifications;
- implementation of an individual and differentiated approach in education.
- formation of basic skills for working with a computer.

It was emphasized above that these technologies are the main tool of the pedagogue today. The formation of logical thinking in future elementary school teachers can give practical results in keeping up with the times in many ways and using modern methods in their practice.

In traditional classes, the teacher offers various games to the students, but faces difficulties in involving all the students in the game, controlling their activities and implementing an individual and differentiated approach. In the process of preparing for such classes, the teacher has difficulty in preparing and collecting demonstration materials. The future pedagogue's awareness of scientific achievements will help him overcome these problems quickly and easily.

Methodological preparation for logical thinking of future elementary school teachers and implementation of pedagogical conditions for the implementation of this issue, in the context of mastering certain subjects in the field of his specialization, in the classroom and outside of the classroom, they are systematic, knowledge-oriented. and opened certain opportunities for the development of communicative competences.

It is appropriate for future elementary school teachers to study the topics in the textbooks of general education schools on this basis, especially to teach the topics of the elementary school mother tongue textbook using information technologies. In the process of training future industry personnel, they should be taught the following:

- use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process;
- to be able to work with multimedia and its technical and software tools;
- to be able to use the basic services and resources of the Internet;
- the use of electronic textbooks in all subjects is desirable, it provides the following opportunities:
 - comprehensive implementation of educational and developmental tasks;
 - setting a special task for each student according to his ability, motivation, level of preparation (depending on the possibilities of ICT tools);
 - use of types of educational electronic means that activate educational activity;
 - partial release of the teacher from the duties of providing information, conducting reinforcement exercises and supervision;
 - forms the student's skills of independent knowledge acquisition; - Developing the skills of collecting, searching and processing information from the Internet;
 - creation of positive educational motivations due to mutual integration of all types of demonstration;
 - organization of developmental exercises and practical training by means of electronic training manual, development of logical and independent thinking in students;

- to enable students to control their knowledge, correct their shortcomings and work independently with the help of developed test tasks;

- implementation of learning activities through rapid feedback and a developed support system.

From the scientific literature, the ability to perceive, imagine and assimilate knowledge is understood as the use of spatial imagination and perception, abstraction, mental images and special views of thinking.

RESULTS

From the point of view of pedagogical conditions and methodology, future pedagogues need to deeply study the following basic concepts as components of logical thinking:

The ability to use puzzle rebuses in non-traditional lessons from the mother tongue and to determine the connections between relationships. The ability to determine all the characteristics of the studied subject, their most important and their interrelationship with other events, and to perform logical tasks. covers the ability.

It means relying on figurative concepts and judgments practical and creative tasks and exercises aimed at developing logical thinking and formal reception of materials, knowledge of mother tongue, skills and

relatively quick and deep acquisition of skills, ability to improve adaptive mental processes, problem-solving tasks describing specific practical issues, and problem-solving skills and abilities are understood.

The ability to reflect is theoretical activity aimed at understanding actions and laws, self-awareness, relying on interdependent logical operations, independence and self-control, understanding induction and deduction methods. and the ability to apply them correctly.

Strengthening ideas about speech, in our opinion, means replacing intuitive ideas with specific constructions, ability to think logically in a numerical and specific field.

From a methodological point of view, the purposeful and systematic development of the important descriptions of mathematical calculation and analytical abilities in the specially organized didactic conditions for the logical thinking of the future elementary school teachers is the basis for the improvement of logical thinking. According to N.F. Talyzina, goals, knowledge, skills and competencies are defined in education, but each skill refers to the tasks solved with the help of this skill. Knowledge is calculated as a specific element of activity and it is formed step by step.

An important aspect of the activity that allows for the creation of pedagogical conditions for the improvement of logical thinking in future elementary school teachers:

the need for learning motives;

organizing independent learning activities;

organization of activity and communication in cooperation;

consists of using the principle of step-by-step formation of mental actions in educational activity.

Improving the logical thinking of future primary school teachers is a complex process due to the pedagogic situation, which requires relying on educational concepts that cover various subject matters, in which there is a link between understanding and practical actions. Communication is important. Individualization of education, didactic synthesis of knowledge, systematization of education, and development of implementation mechanisms based on the principles of educational formalization are becoming the main goals of modern pedagogy.

DISCUSSION

Methodological training for logical thinking in future elementary school teachers and improvement of their logical thinking involves a high level of mental operations (analysis, synthesis, abstraction, generalization and practical application), economy and independence of thinking, and its flexibility. .

In the process of primary education, the future teacher tries to explain his goals through the task of understanding the goals of the problem and its implementation, by independently explaining problematic situations. At the same time, his understanding of the students, understanding of their goals, directing their spiritual, mental, and physical abilities to a certain goal, makes it possible for them to acquire knowledge, practical skills and skills, develop knowledge, and develop speech. In this process, as a result of perfect mastery of psychology, pedagogy and didactics, the future elementary school teacher will be able to distinguish various problems, find ways and forms of education, study the causes of student's shortcomings based on analysis, responsibilities The content and methods of each training are developed by being able to feel, hardworking, controlling the results of one's work, relying on national and universal values. The teacher's scientific competence, the availability of educational and didactic materials, their content and quality, the recognition of their achievements by other teachers, and the effectiveness of using modern information and communication technologies condition for - creation of conditions, organization of practical training seminars to reveal the essence of the creative activity process, achieving deep and thorough assimilation of the scientific basis of the current approach to the educational process of scientific and technical innovations, new to the organization of creative activities internal approach formation, planning of creative activities and improving the skills of creative work are considered important in ensuring the effectiveness of education.

CONCLUSION

In short, the outlook, thinking and logical thinking characteristics of the future elementary school teacher are determined by the strength, speed, depth of acquiring methods and styles in the educational process, and the assessment of students' knowledge. Pedagogical conditions and didactic support for preparing future elementary school teachers for logical thinking, individual characteristics, ideas, research, teacher and student relations, intellectual aspects, educational qualities of these processes contributed to the development.

REFERENCES

1. Toshpulatova Sh.O O'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish (Fizika darslari misolida). Diss..Ped. fan PhD Samarqand – 2019 19-b
2. Utemov V. V., Zinovkina M. M., Gorev P. M. Ijodkorlik pedagogikasi: ilmiy ijodkorlikning amaliy kursi: darslik. - Kirov: ANOO "Hududlararo CITO", 2013. - 212 p.
3. Mahmudov M.H. Ta'limni didaktik loyihalashning nazariy asoslari. Ped. fan. doktorlik. diss. . . –Toshkent, 2003. 342b.
4. . Maftuna, G. (2021). Effective ways to Use Triz (The Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) in Elementary School. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 9, 85-88.
5. Ganieva, M. (2023). EMPOWERING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH TIPS TECHNOLOGY. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 12, pp. 62-63).

6. Maftuna, G. (2023). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR LOGICAL THINKING. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 91-94.
7. Ganiyeva, M. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFI O'QUVCHILARINI MANTIQUIY TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DIDAKTIK O'YINLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI. TA'LIM FIDOYILARI.
8. Ganiyeva, M. (2023). INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA, O'QUVCHILARNI MANTIQUIY FIKRLASHGA O'RGATISHNING, SHAKL, METOD VA VOSITALARI. Scienceweb academic papers collection.